

Table 2. Summary of bat acoustic surveys conducted in the North Sea of Europe.

Source	Site	Distance from land (km)	Number of detectors	Height (m)	Structure	Survey dates	Number of nights	Total passes	Maximum passes	Overall rate ^a
Lagerveld et al. 2014	Offshore Wind Farm Egmond aan Zee	15	1	15	Wind turbine	08/29/12- 10/20/12	53	189	70	3.57
	Princess Amalia Windpark	25	1	15	Wind turbine	09/04/12- 09/23/12	20	25	10	1.25
Lagerveld et al. 2015	Luchterduinen	23	1	15	Wind turbine	03/02/15- 10/09/15	220	11	8	0.05
	Princess Amalia Windpark	25	1	15	Wind turbine	03/23/15- 10/20/15	205	15	7	0.07
Hüppop and Hill 2016	FINO1	45	1	20	Research platform	08/12/04- 12/31/15	3530	317		0.09
Brabant et al. 2019	Thorntonbank Wind Farm	27	7	16	Wind turbine base	08/08/17- 11/30/17	798	142		0.18 ^b
			4	93	Wind turbine nacelle	08/08/17- 11/30/17	456	9		0.02 ^b

^a passes/detector-night

^b detectors programmed to only record bats that emitted echolocation calls > 30 kHz